

Instagram Usage, Physical Appearance Comparison and Self-Esteem among Adolescents in Lunglei

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Abstract

Social Networking Sites particularly Instagram is now an vital part of the daily lives of the adolescent population. This study attempts to analyzing the relationship between Instagram usage and self-esteem among adolescents with a focus on exploring how exposure to Instagram influence body image and self-esteem. The study is descriptive in design and mixed method in nature. The sample size is 80 in which stratified proportionate sampling method was used to collect data. Intensity of Instagram usage, Physical Appearance Comparison and Self-Esteem levels were measured. The result of the study indicates that Instagram users are likely to exhibit signs of addiction, with many spending 3-4 hours a day on social media despite long school hours. Experiencing physical appearance comparison is low with no gender differences related to social media, in addition, self-esteem levels remained low. There is a significant relationship between social media addiction, physical appearance comparison and self-esteem among the adolescents. The study highlights the need for greater awareness of social media's potential harms, especially regarding screen time and body image concerns. Future research should continue to explore these impacts and promote healthier usage.

Keywords: Adolescents, Instagram usage, physical body comparison, self esteem

Introduction

Instagram is a social media platform where users can share photos and videos, as well as engage with others through likes, comments, and direct messaging. The name "Instagram" is combination of two words "instant" meaning to the instant sharing of moments and experiences and "gram" short for "telegram", referring to a quick and concise message. Instagram, one of the most popular social media platforms, has

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been found to have a significant impact on the self-esteem of its users. With over a billion active users, Instagram has become a breeding ground for comparison, competition, and self-doubt.

Self-esteem is an individual's total feeling of self-worth, including their perceived value, strengths, and limitations. Adolescents' self-esteem is especially subject to environmental influences, making high school students an important group to examine.

Physical Appearance Comparison and social media platforms have a complicated relationship. Instagram, Facebook, and Twitter, for example, can promote body comparison and negative body image through curated material, social comparison, beauty ideals, and cyberbullying. Users are frequently exposed to modified and manipulated photographs that promote unrealistic beauty standards, causing feelings of inadequacy and low self-esteem.

Overview of Literature

Young adults showed high Instagram usage intensity with high levels of self-esteem. There is no significant correlation between the intensity of Instagram usage and self-esteem. (Hidayah, R & Aryandari, K, 2021; Hidayah, N & Hasbullah, H, 2024)

There is no significant difference between active users and non-active users of Instagram with relation to social comparison and self-esteem. But the youth have low self-esteem and a high tendency to make social comparisons while using Instagram. (Mayukh, N. et al. 2022).

Meanwhile, studies indicate significant relationship between the intensity of Instagram usage and self-esteem among youth. (Uddin Md, S & Wok, S 2020; Sekarlagit M, C, et al. 2022; Fernandez K, M, 2023; Favini, A., et al 2024).

Researchers explored the impact of Instagram on body image among the youth. Several studies suggest that Instagram use increases concerns about body image and physical appearance among female adolescents which results in comparison and poor self-image (Pedalino, F., & Camerini, A.-L. 2022; Alfonso-Fuertes et.al 2023)

Also, studies revealed that people who spent more time on Instagram reported higher levels of body dissatisfaction, increased physical comparisons, and worse self-esteem. (Jiang, S & Ngien, A 2020; Han, Z, et al. 2021; Jarman, H, K., et al. 2022; Feurtes A, I., et al. 2023, Vikram, A & Sutar, D. 2024.)

Statement of the problem

Despite Instagram's widespread popularity among adolescents, there is growing concern that excessive usage of the platform may be detrimental to their self-esteem, as they are constantly exposed to curated and manipulated content that perpetuates unrealistic beauty standards, promotes consumerism, and fosters competition and comparison. However, there is a lack of comprehensive research on the specific impact of Instagram on self-esteem among adolescents, particularly in Mizoram, and how this impact varies across international, national, and local contexts.

This study aims to address this knowledge gap by investigating the relationship between Instagram usage, physical appearance comparison and self-esteem among adolescents with a focus on identifying the factors that contribute to this relationship and the implications for their mental health and well-being.

Methodology

Research design

The study was conducted at Baptist Higher Secondary School (BHSS) located in Serkawn, Lunglei; Mizoram. Adolescents that are attending schooling in higher secondary school represent the universe of the study. Class 12 Arts section 'A' represent the population of the present study. This study is descriptive in design and followed mixed methods of data in nature.

Sampling

For the purpose of this study, stratified proportionate sampling technique was employed in identifying the respondents for the study from the school. The sample size consisted of 80 samples from class 12 Arts section 'A' students, which represent the overall population of the schools. Thus, the overall sample size comprised of 80 students, with 40 male and 40 female students selected from the school.

Tools

Structured questionnaire was used for collection of primary data. The questionnaire is divided into five sections that includes profile of the respondents, Instagram intensity, Social Media Addiction, Physical Appearance Comparison and Self-esteem.

Scales

Rosenberg Self-esteem scale was used to measure the levels of self-esteem with reliability test at .605 Cronbach Alpha. The scale is a 10-item instrument consisting of statements. All items are answered using a 4-point Likert scale format ranging from “Strongly agree” to “Strongly disagree”.

To measure Social Media Addiction, the Bergen social media addiction scale was used. Social media addiction is operationalized based on six symptoms indicative of addiction (salience, conflict, mood modification, withdrawal, tolerance, and relapse). The scale assesses addiction with 6 items on a 5-point Likert scale ranging from “Very rarely” to “Very often”. The reliability of the scale stands at .688 Cronbach Alpha.

The Physical Appearance Comparison Scale - *Revised Version* (PACS-R) developed by Shaefer & Thompson, 2014 was used to measure respondents’ awareness to physical appearance. The scale is a 11-item instrument consisting of five (05) domains like comparison of weight, body size, body shape, body fat and overall appearance. All items are answered using a 5-point Likert scale format ranging from “never” to “always”. The reliability of the scale range stands at .920 Cronbach Alpha.

Results and discussions

This section deals with the results and discussion of the study. They are structured into six parts. They are profile of the respondents, Instagram intensity, social media addiction, physical appearance comparison, levels of self-esteem and inter correlation matrix.

Profile of the respondents

Profile of the respondents is presented into categories viz. age group and socio-economic base.

The findings reveal that a vast majority (85.0%) falls in the age group between 16-18. The mean age for male is 18.10 while it is 17.65 for female, and the overall mean age is 17.87. More than two-thirds (68.8%) of the respondents belong to APL families, with males (41.3%) slightly outnumbering females (27.5%).

Table 1: Profile of the respondents

S/N	Variables	Gender		Total
		Male	Female	N=80
		n=40	n=40	
I	Age group			
	16-18	31 (38.80)	37 (46.30)	68 (85)
	19-21	9 (11.30)	3 (3.80)	12 (15)
	<i>Mean age</i>	<i>18.1</i>	<i>17.65</i>	<i>17.87</i>
II	Socio economic base			
	APL	33 (41.30)	22 (27.50)	55 (68.80)
	PHH	6 (7.50)	14 (17.50)	20 (25)
	Non-NFSA	1 (1.30)	4 (5)	5 (6.30)

Source: Computed Figures in parenthesis percentages

Instagram Intensity

Table 2 shows Instagram Intensity that is grouped into motives and time spent on Instagram.

Based on the findings, more than half (53.8%) utilize Instagram for entertainment. On average, 26.3% of the respondents spend around 3-4 hours per day on Instagram. This signifies that there is room for improvement in using Instagram especially among the male population which are spending more time on the screen than the female. Likewise, excessive screen time raises concerns about its effect on physical health and productivity.

Table 2: Instagram intensity

S/N	Variables	Gender		Total N=80
		Male n=40	Female n=40	
I	Motives for using Instagram			
	Entertainment	19 (23.8)	24 (30)	43 (53.8)
	Communication	13 (16.3)	8 (10)	21 (26.3)
	Time pass	3 (3.8)	3 (3.8)	6 (7.5)
	Keeping in pace with others	0 (0)	1 (1.3)	1 (1.3)
	Knowledge and creativity	4 (5)	4 (5)	8 (10)
	Others	1 (1.3)	0 (0)	1 (1.3)
II	Average time spent on Instagram per day			
	Less than 1 hour	9 (11.3)	7 (8.8)	16 (20)
	1-2 hours	12 (15)	4 (5)	16 (20)
	3-4 hours	12 (15)	9 (11.3)	21 (26.3)
	4-5 hours	4 (5)	11 (13.8)	15 (18.8)
	More than 5 hours	3 (3.8)	9 (11.3)	12 (15)

Source: Computed Figures in parenthesis are percentages

Social Media Addiction

Table 3 represents the Levels of Social Media Addiction which is distributed as very low, low, high and very high. The majority (52.5%) fall in low (13-18) level in which female are more (28.8%). A few (23.8%) fits in very low level which is compose of male. The remaining are 3.8 percent scores very high in which female is more (2.5%) than male (1.35%).

The findings reveal that there is less to worry about social media addiction among both the genders as the table shows low level of addiction.

Table 3: Levels of Social Media Addiction

Levels of Social Media Addiction	Gender		Total N=80
	Male n=40	Female n=40	
Very low (6-12)	9	4	13
	(11.3)	(5)	(16.3)
Low (13-18)	19	23	42
	(23.8)	(28.8)	(52.5)
High (19-24)	11	11	22
	(13.8)	(13.8)	(27.5)
Very High (24 above)	1	2	3
	(1.3)	(2.5)	(3.8)

Source: Computed Figures in parenthesis are percentages

Physical Appearance Comparison

Table 4 shows respondents’ awareness towards Physical Appearance Comparison by gender using T-test distribution. Physical Awareness is categorized into eleven (11) domains. Among the respondents’ mean scores, the majority (3) is ‘*When I am out in public, I compare my physical appearance to the appearance of others*’ in which female (3.15) is more than male (2.85).

The T-test analysis reveals that there are no significant gender differences between male and female with regards to awareness of Physical Appearance Comparison as they both are showing signs of contentment and calmness to their physical appearances in general which is similar to the findings of Han, Z, et.al., 2022.

Table 4: PACS-R domains by gender

PACS-R	Male		Female		Total		t value	P value
	n=40		n=40		N=80			
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD		
When I am out in public, I compare my physical appearance to the appearance of others	2.85	1.12	3.15	1.27	3.00	1.20	-1.119	.267
When I meet a new person (same sex) , I compare my body size to his/her body size.	2.88	1.11	2.85	1.33	2.86	1.22	.091	.928
When I am at work or school, I compare my body shape to the body shape of others.	2.40	1.03	2.83	1.32	2.61	1.20	-1.605	.113
When I am out in public, I compare my body fat to the body fat of others.	2.18	1.20	2.55	1.30	2.36	1.26	-1.343	.183
When I am shopping for clothes, I compare my weight to the weight of others.	2.10	1.17	2.38	1.35	2.24	1.27	-.972	.334
When I am at a party, I compare my body shape to the body shape of others.	2.05	1.24	2.23	1.35	2.14	1.29	-.604	.547
When I am eating in a restaurant, I compare my body shape to the body shape of others.	1.98	1.03	2.35	1.39	2.16	1.23	-1.375	.173
When I am with a group of friends, I compare my body size to the body size of others.	2.40	1.10	2.70	1.20	2.55	1.16	-1.162	.249
When I am eating in a restaurant, I compare my body fat to the body fat of others.	1.95	1.04	2.23	1.29	2.09	1.17	-1.051	.297
When I am at the gym, I compare my physical appearance to the appearance of others.	2.25	1.08	1.88	1.30	2.06	1.20	1.400	.165

Source: Computed *p<0.05 **p<0.05

Levels of Self-esteem

Table 5 represents the Levels of Self-Esteem. The table is distributed as low and normal with regards to total score. Majority (63.8%) scores low, with male are a little less than one-third (31.3%) and female a little more than male (32.5%). The remaining (36.3%) percent scores normal in which male are a little less than one-fifth (18.8%) and a few of female (1.3%).

This shows that the levels of self-esteem among the respondents is low which could be an impact of their exposure to Instagram mostly due to physical body comparisons.

Table 5 Levels of Self-esteem

Levels of Self esteem	Gender		Total
	Male	Female	
	n=40	n=40	N=80
Low (<15)	25 (31.3)	26 (32.5)	51 (63.8)
Normal (16-25)	15 (18.8)	14 (17.5)	29 (36.3)

Source: Computed Figures in parenthesis are percentages

Inter Correlation Matrix

Research findings show a positive correlation between social media addiction with physical appearance comparison at .447** and self-esteem at .230* which is similar to findings of Vikram, A & Sutar, D. 2024.

This indicate that exposure to social media is affecting the adolescents psychologically by comparing their physical appearance with others which creates insecurity and craving for being liked by others on social media platforms especially on Instagram. Moreover, the perception of self, that is self-esteem is largely affected by adolescents’ engagement in social media platforms.

Table 6: Inter correlation matrix of screen time, SMA, PAC and self-esteem.

Variables	Screen time	Social Media Addiction	Physical Appearance Comparison	Self esteem
Screen time	1			
Social Media Addiction	.110	1		
Physical Appearance Comparison	.205	.447**	1	
Self esteem	.025	.230*	.064	1

*Correlation is significant at 0.05 level **Correlation is significant at 0.01 level

Conclusion

Understanding how to navigate social media effectively is of extreme importance since it has become an essential component of daily existence. Its impact on social, physical, mental health, and the economy suggest further research to understand its broader effects. The findings of the study shows that Instagram users are more likely to exhibit signs of addiction, with many spending 3-4 hours a day on social media despite long school hours. This excessive screen time raises concerns about its effect on physical health and productivity. Experiencing physical appearance comparison is low with no gender differences related to social media, in addition, self-esteem levels remained low. There is a significant relationship between social media addiction, physical appearance comparison and self-esteem among the adolescents. The study highlights the need for greater awareness of social media's potential harms, especially regarding screen time and body image concerns. Future research should continue to explore these impacts and promote healthier usage.

Implications of the study

The study could be beneficial in determining the efficacy of screen time management strategies, evaluating the influence of social media on self-esteem across varied socioeconomic backgrounds, and, more broadly, devising focused interventions to address social media-related concerns.

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